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STEM Graduates in the Italian Regions in the Period 2012-2020

Between 2012 and 2020 they grew by 22.58%

Istat calculates the value of people who obtain a STEM tertiary qualification in the year. This value is constituted by the ratio between residents in the region who obtained a tertiary level qualification in scientific-technological disciplines in the reference calendar year and the population aged 20-29 years of the same region per thousand. The numerator includes graduates, research doctors, graduates of the ITIS level I and II level master's specialization courses, who have obtained the title in the disciplinary areas of Natural Sciences, Physics, Mathematics, Statistics, Computer Science, and Engineering information, Industrial Engineering, Architecture and Civil Engineering.

Ranking of people obtaining a STEM tertiary qualification in 2020. Molise is in first place in terms of value of people obtaining a STEM tertiary qualification in 2020 with an amount equal to 21.50 units, followed by Abruzzo with a amount of 19.70 units, from Friuli Venezia Giulia with an amount of 18.50 units. In the middle of the table are Veneto with an amount of 16.70 units, followed by Emilia Romagna with a value of 16.50 units and Piedmont with a value of 16.40 units. Sardinia closes the ranking with an amount of 13.50 units, followed by Valle d'Aosta with an amount of 12.40 units and Trentino Alto Adige with a value of 8.40 units.

Ranking of the Italian regions by value of the change in the value of people with STEM qualifications between 2012 and 2022. Molise is in first place by value of the percentage change in people who obtain a STEM qualification between 2012 and 2020 with a value equal to 62.88% equivalent to a growth from an amount of 13.20 units up to a value of 21.50 units equal to an amount of 8.30 units. Puglia follows with a percentage change value equal to an amount of 44.55% or equivalent to a growth from an amount of 11.00 units up to a value of 15.90 units equal to a value of 4.90 units. Below is Basilicata with a value equal to an amount of 42.97% or equal to a variation from an amount of 12.80 units up to a value of 18.30 equal to a growth of 5.50 units.

In the middle of the ranking is Veneto with an amount of 21.90% equal to a variation from an amount of 13.70 units up to a value of 16.70 units or equal to a value of 3.00 units. Liguria follows with a variation equal to an amount of 20.55% equivalent to a variation from an amount of 14.60 units up to a value of 17.60 units equal to an amount of 3.00 units. Below is Lazio with a variation equal to an amount of 20.53% equivalent to a variation equal to an amount of 15.10 units up to a value of 18.20 units equivalent to a variation equal to an amount of 3.10 units.

Tuscany closes the ranking with a variation equal to an amount of 6.15% equivalent to a variation from an amount of 13.00 units up to a value of 13.80 units equal to an amount of 0.80 units. Valle d'Aosta follows with a variation equal to an amount of 3.33% equal to a variation from an amount of

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12.00 units up to a value of 12.40 units. Trentino Alto Adige closes the ranking with a variation equal to an amount of -1.18% equal to a variation from an amount of 8.50 units up to a value of 8.40 units equal to a value of -0.10 unit.

Overall, between 2012 and 2020 the value of STEM graduates on average in the Italian regions grew from an amount of 13.19 units up to a value of 16.17 units or equal to an amount of 2.98 units equal to an amount by 22.58%.

STEM graduates in the Italian macro-regions between 2012 and 2020. The value of STEM graduates in Northern Italy grew from an amount of 13.6 units up to a value of 154.8 units or a variation equal to an amount of 2.20 units equal to +16.18%. The value of STEM graduates in North-West Italy grew from an amount of 13.6 units up to a value of 15.7 units or equal to a variation of 2.10 units equal to an amount of 15.44%. The value of STEM graduates in the North-East grew from an amount of 13.5 units up to a value of 15.9 units or equal to a variation of 2.40 units equal to a variation of 17.78%. The value of STEM graduates in Central Italy grew from an amount of 14.5 units up to a value of 16.8 units equal to a variation of 2.30 units equal to an amount of +15.86%. The value of STEM graduates in the South grew from an amount of 11.7 units up to a value of 15.5 units or equal to an amount of 3.80 units equal to a value of +32.48%.

Clustering with k-Means algorithm optimized with the Silhouette coefficient. Below we present a clustering with k-Means algorithm optimized with the Silhouette coefficient. The data shows the presence of two clusters:

- Cluster 1: Liguria, Lazio, Emilia Romagna, Abruzzo, Friuli Venezia Giulia, Marche, Basilicata, Molise, Veneto, Umbria, Calabria, Piedmont, Lombardy;
- Cluster 2: Sicily, Valle d'Aosta, Sardinia, Trentino Alto Adige, Tuscany, Puglia, Campania.

We can note that Cluster 1 is dominant compared to the value of Cluster 2. However, we can note that it is not possible to identify a clear distinction between regions of the Centre-North and regions of the Centre-South. Furthermore, the two clusters are both heterogeneous from a per capita income point of view. It follows that the distinction between dominant regions in terms of the value of STEM graduates and regions with a low value of STEM graduates depends neither on geographical reasons nor on strictly economic-financial reasons. It is very likely, however, that there are determinants of a sociological, cultural and industrial nature that justify investment in STEM disciplines. We note for example that even the university structure is not a signal for the growth of STEM graduates. In fact, we note that Puglia, which even has a Polytechnic, still has low values in terms of STEM graduates. Puglia is in the cluster of regions that have low numbers of STEM graduates.

Conclusions. The value of STEM graduates grew in all Italian regions between 2012 and 2020 with the exception of Trentino Alto Adige which recorded a slight negative decline of -1.18%. On average in 2020, approximately 16.17% of graduates in the 20-29 age group acquired a qualification in STEM disciplines. This is a very small value and implicitly indicates that approximately 83.83% of students have obtained a degree in non-STEM disciplines. The number of graduates in STEM disciplines should grow consistently with the objectives of industrialization 4.0, digitalization and the application of organizational and managerial tools inspired by technological innovation and research and development. In this regard, it is necessary to completely change the Italian education system to ensure that graduates in STEM disciplines are increased in order to allow the technological and cognitive advancement of the country of Italy.

Declarations

Data Availability Statement. The data presented in this study are available on request from the corresponding author.

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Declaration of Competing Interest. The author declares that there is no conflict of interests regarding the publication of this manuscript. In addition, the ethical issues, including plagiarism, informed consent, misconduct, data fabrication and/or falsification, double publication.

Software. The authors have used the following software: Gretl for the econometric models, Orange for clusterization and network analysis, and KNIME for machine learning and predictions. They are all free version without licenses.

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Appendix

Macro Regioni	2012	2020	Var Ass	Var Per
Nord	13,6	15,8	2,20	16,18
Nord-ovest	13,6	15,7	2,10	15,44
Nord-est	13,5	15,9	2,40	17,78
Centro	14,5	16,8	2,30	15,86
Mezzogiorno	11,7	15,5	3,80	32,48

Laureti nelle Discipline STEM tra il 2012 ed il 2020

Regioni	2012	2013	2014	2015	2016	2017	2018	2019	2020
Piemonte	14,20	14,20	14,40	13,80	13,10	13,80	14,40	15,00	16,40
Valle d'Aosta	12,00	10,60	10,80	12,70	11,30	11,30	9,50	12,10	12,40
Liguria	14,60	15,70	14,60	15,10	15,50	15,60	16,70	16,70	17,60
Lombardia	13,30	13,80	13,90	13,20	13,40	13,90	14,10	15,00	15,30
Trentino-Alto Adige	8,50	9,30	9,10	8,60	8,10	7,70	7,90	8,50	8,40
Veneto	13,70	13,90	14,00	13,50	14,90	15,10	15,60	16,10	16,70
Friuli-Venezia Giulia	16,60	16,20	15,70	15,20	16,20	15,50	16,20	16,10	18,50
Emilia-Romagna	14,00	14,70	15,00	14,80	15,80	15,60	15,40	16,80	16,50
Toscana	13,00	12,60	12,00	12,30	12,80	12,30	13,30	14,00	13,80
Umbria	12,80	13,50	13,00	14,30	15,00	15,20	16,00	16,60	17,00
Marche	16,80	15,60	15,90	17,30	16,80	17,10	17,60	17,70	18,40
Lazio	15,10	15,40	14,10	14,60	15,10	15,70	16,30	18,00	18,20
Abruzzo	15,00	14,90	15,00	16,10	17,20	17,60	18,20	18,90	19,70
Molise	13,20	14,20	16,20	16,50	16,60	18,20	18,90	19,70	21,50
Campania	12,10	12,10	12,40	13,10	13,70	13,90	15,20	15,80	15,90
Puglia	11,00	11,10	11,40	11,70	13,50	13,60	14,50	15,70	15,90
Basilicata	12,80	13,90	14,30	15,30	15,90	17,40	18,00	17,90	18,30
Calabria	13,90	14,00	14,20	13,50	14,10	14,80	14,40	15,90	16,00
Sicilia	10,40	10,70	10,20	10,40	10,90	11,30	11,50	12,70	13,50
Sardegna	10,90	12,00	12,00	11,80	12,00	12,70	12,80	14,00	13,50

